

Synthesis of some 2-(*N'*-Arylcarbamoylmethyl)hydrazino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines

M. K. JANI, N. K. UNDAVIA and P. B. TRIVEDI*

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

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Some 2-(*N'*-arylcarbamoylmethyl)hydrazino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines have been prepared by the reaction of 2-hydrazinopyrimidine and various *N*-chloroacetylated amines, and screened for their antimicrobial activities.

HYDRAZINE derivatives of pyrimidine are found to possess various biological activities¹. Keeping these observations in view, we have undertaken synthesis of 2-(*N'*-arylcarbamoylmethyl)hydrazino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines and studied their antibacterial and antitubercular activities. The compounds were synthesised according to the sequence of reactions outlined in Scheme 1.

2-(*N'*-Arylcarbamoylmethyl)hydrazino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and appropriate *N*-chloroacetylated amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3–4 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1): $\lambda_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 565 (C=C), 1 620 (C=N), 2 960 (CH), 1 680 (C=O non-cyclic), 3 280 (NH), 3 640 (OH) and 840 cm^{-1} (1,3-disubstituted-benzene).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesised compounds were checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pekin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

N-Chloroacetylated amines were prepared by following the reported method². 2-Mercapto-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (1) was prepared from ethyl acetoacetate and thiourea in presence of potassium carbonate³. 2-Hydrazino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (2) was prepared by the reported method⁴.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂	177	60
2.	3-OH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂	141	66
3.	4-OH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂	138	64
4.	2-OOH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	166	57
5.	3-OOH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	204	53
6.	4-OOH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	178	59
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃	186	69
8.	4 OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃	151	71
9.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ O ₂	124	54
10.	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ O ₂	185	54
11.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ O ₂	171	58
12.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₄	191	62
13.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₄	160	60
14.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₄	190	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Pharmacological screening :

The synthesised compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Results and Discussion

Antibacterial activity : Out of the 14 compounds tested, 6 compounds were found to be active against Gram+ve bacteria (*S. aureus*) and 5 compounds active against Gram-ve bacteria (*E. coli*) and 4 compounds active against both the species. 4-Substituted-phenyl compounds were found to be

most active against both the species. All 3-substituted-phenyl substituents were found inactive, except 3-chlorophenyl substituent which was active against *E. coli*. Compounds having 4-methylphenyl, 2-methoxyphenyl, 4-ethoxyphenyl and 4-nitrophenyl substituents were found active against both the species (Table 2).

(100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). 4-Chlorophenyl substituent was found to be effective at higher concentration (Table 2).

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TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY DATA* OF COMPOUNDS 3

Sl. no.	Antibacterial activity		Antitubercular activity concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	35	100
1.	+	-	Not screened	
2.	-	-	+	+
3.	+	+	+	+
4.	+	+	+	+
5.	-	-	Not screened	
6.	-	-	Not screened	
7.	-	-	Not screened	
8.	+	+	+	+
9.	-	+	Not screened	
10.	-	-	Not screened	
11.	+	-	+	-
12.	-	-	Not screened	
13.	-	-	Not screened	
14.	+	+	+	+

*For antibacterial activity: (+) =inhibition zone, (-) =no inhibition zone; for antitubercular activity: (-) =effective, (+) =not effective.

Antitubercular activity : Out of the 6 compounds screened, not a single compound was found effective at lower concentration (35 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$); but one compound was effective at higher concentration

References

1. D. VAN, V. CLAESSEN and D. E. SOMER, *Antibiotics and Chemotherapy*, 1959, **9**, 523; YU. A. AZEV, I. I. MUDRETSOVA, A. F. GOLENEVA and G. A. ALEKSANDROVA, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1987, **21**, 1446 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 142851); K. KONISHI, T. KURAGANO and K. MATSURA, *Jap. Pat.* 61 268 669/1986 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 176181); H. MORITA, T. AOZUKA and K. TAKAGI, *Jap. Pat.* 61 205 260/1986 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 33103); H. FUJIWARA, T. TAMURA, H. TAGAMI, D. TAKASHI, R. SANO and Y. KITAZONO, *Jap. Pat.* 62 263 179/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 167497); P. D. MOMASTER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1979, **22**, 1177; W. BRANDES, W. DAUM and P. KRAUS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 120822; G. O'DOHERTY, *US Pat.* 7 524 517/1975; Y. ITO, H. KATO, E. ETSUCHU, N. OGAVA and T. YOSHIDA, *Jap. Pat.* 62 242 675/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 204639).
2. W. A. JACOB, M. HEIDALBERGER and I. P. REIF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 458.
3. SIMONE and LEVSHINA, *Tr. Ukr. Nauch. Issled. Inst. Eksp. Endokrinol.*, 1965, **20**, 193 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1967, **66**, 85752).
4. G. T. LONG, W. W. LEE and GOODMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 1867.